

| CORRIGENDUM

Fera, M., Fruggiero, F., Lambiase, A., & Macchiaroli, R. (2016). State of the art of additive manufacturing: Review for tolerances, mechanical resistance and production costs. *Cogent Engineering*, 3, DOI: [10.1080/23311916.2016.1261503](https://doi.org/10.1080/23311916.2016.1261503)

The fourth author's name appeared in error as "Maccharoli, R.". This has now been corrected to "Macchiaroli, R." in the final Version of Record online. The authors apologize for this error.

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